

"CHALLENGES, SOLUTIONS, AND PROSPECTS FOR THE EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN GENERAL EDUCATION SCHOOLS"

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Abstract: This article details the current state of inclusive education in general education schools, as well as the problems and shortcomings in organizing educational processes, and provides necessary solutions and recommendations using the latest modern methods. Also, pedagogical, psychological, and organizational recommendations have been developed that strengthen the integration of children with special needs into the quality educational process.

Keywords: inclusive education, children with special needs, integration, special educator, speech therapist, defectologist, deaf educator, child psychologist, smart classroom, AR/VR classrooms.

Introduction: In recent years, the implementation of the methodological foundations of inclusivity in Uzbekistan's education system has been identified as a priority in state policy. In the current education system of New Uzbekistan, inclusive education is one of the rapidly developing areas, creating new educational opportunities for today.

In particular, based on the Presidential Decree "On measures to further improve the system of education and upbringing for children with special educational needs," various projects and modern educational programs aimed at organizing inclusive education and improving the quality of educational services provided to them are one of the most important issues today.

Nevertheless, in the process of effective implementation of inclusive education, a number of issues remain regarding the training of teaching staff, the material and technical base, the assessment system, as well as the socio-psychological environment between inclusive education participants and healthy children. This article is aimed at conducting an in-depth scientific analysis of these problems and developing proposals based on real pedagogical practice.

Main part: Inclusive education is an educational system that began to be studied and implemented on a global scale 50–100 years ago or even earlier, whereas this term was introduced to us in the next 5–10 years and is becoming a popular direction of the education system.

In particular, in Uzbekistan, a number of scientists, such as F.U. Kodirova, Sh.N. Ibadullaeva, F.R. Teshaboeva, U. Yuldashev, and M.B. Ataboeva, have made their immense contribution to the development of inclusive education. During my studies and research in our field, I came to the conclusion that "Inclusive education is an educational philosophy and practice aimed at creating equal opportunities for all students to receive a quality education, regardless of their abilities, needs and characteristics." The effective organization of inclusive educational processes in general education schools is of great importance for involving every member of society in full-fledged social life and for creating an atmosphere of tolerance and mutual respect. Today, healthy children and children with special needs are studying together

in general education schools. **We divide children involved in inclusive education into the following groups:**

- Children with hearing, vision, speech, and musculoskeletal disorders;
- Children with intellectual disabilities;
- Children with autism spectrum disorders (ASD);
- Children with behavioral and emotional disorders;
- Children with learning difficulties (dyslexia, dyscalculia, etc.);

This creates a need for modern methodologies, adapted programs, and the cooperation of multidisciplinary specialists within the education system. It is not expected that a newly implemented system will immediately demonstrate high efficiency in any operational process. To achieve stable and effective results, a certain amount of time, financial resources, and practical experience must be accumulated. **The following problems are also observed in inclusive education:**

a) shortage of personnel: with the opening of inclusive classes in general education schools, there is a need for specialized specialists such as teachers, defectologists, deaf educators, speech therapists, and child psychologists. Currently, the aforementioned shortage of qualified personnel is one of the primary issues.

b) lack of special training of teachers: the lack of special knowledge and skills of ordinary class teachers to work with children with special educational needs is an aspect that should be given special attention.

d) problems with the material and technical base and infrastructure: the buildings of most general education schools are not adapted for children with disabilities (elevators, special ramps for wheelchairs, special toilets). As an example, we can cite the lack of special educational and methodological materials and technical means (Braille books, smart boards, hearing aids, special computer equipment and programs) intended for children with special needs.

e) lack of educational resources and textbooks: insufficient methodological manuals for the inclusive education program and simplified textbooks for children with special needs. This includes the absence of separate educational programs and plans based on the individual capabilities of each child.

Socio-psychological problems: Healthy children and their parents do not always have a healthy opinion and attitude toward a student in an inclusive education system. It is natural that this newly introduced system will not be met with a healthy view and a healthy attitude in a short time, but it is necessary to correctly assess the situation and adapt to the process with a subjective approach. This is because the influence of healthy people plays an important role in the socialization and communication of inclusive education participants.

The gradual implementation of this system in our society will allow for the identification and improvement of various organizational and pedagogical constraints arising in this process, as well as effective mechanisms for their elimination. In global practice, countries such as Finland, Canada, Japan, and South Korea are successfully implementing inclusive education. From the practical implementation of this system, the aforementioned countries have drawn the following conclusions: "Every child has the opportunity to realize their talents and potential. They participate directly in the process, feeling that the educational system is adapted to them, not to education".

I. As part of my scientific research, I analytically studied advanced foreign experiences in forming inclusive education practices - specifically the modules and technologies used in the education systems of Finland and Canada - and examined their practical aspects based on a comparative approach.

II. Finland is one of the countries with the most effective inclusive education system in the world, and although this education system has developed in several main stages, the main legislative changes and systematic implementation began in the late 1980s and early 1990s, when the idea of inclusion was officially adopted and began to be implemented in schools in the 1990s, but the transition to full education continued in the 2000s, especially in the 2010s. In the Finnish model, a "three-stage system of additional assistance" has been implemented, with the following technologies widely implemented:

III. "Co-teaching – bir sinfda ikki o'qituvchi ishlashi (bu sistemada oddiy sinf o'qituvchisi va maxsus ta'lim mutaxassisi birgalikda ishlash tamoyili belgilangan).

IV. "Assistive technology" - technical capabilities that help a child be independent, understand the lesson, and actively participate in the classroom (for example, audio books - help children with visual difficulties or slow reading pace learn the lesson text by listening).

V. "LukiMat" - an individual reading platform (this platform assesses a student's reading pace, memorization, word recognition, and phonemic skills, and provides individual exercises corresponding to these results).

VI. "Ecology" platform - For children who have difficulty distinguishing letters (for example, a sound is heard near the screen, and the child must press the corresponding letter). Such games are very effective in working with dyslexia.

As one of the world's most developed and social justice-oriented nations, Canada considers inclusion a priority of its educational policy. In the country, every child has the right to a quality education, regardless of their physical, mental, or psychological needs. To this end, inclusion in Canadian schools is organized based on the principle of adapting the entire education system to the needs of the student, rather than just children with special needs. In the Canadian model, an "Individual Development Profile for Each Child" was created:

Individual Education Plan (IEP) - a set of specific plans with specific goals for each child with special needs;
Peer-support (peer helpers) - healthy classmates support and help children with special needs;
Smart-classroom technology is a digital environment where technology helps adapt the lesson process to the student's needs, present educational materials in various formats, and provide precise monitoring for the teacher;
Autiplay, ABC mouse - an educational platform for children with learning difficulties through animation, sound and games;
VR simulators (virtual reality) are a technology that teaches a child to adapt to social life in a safe and playful way.

Several achievements have been made in developed countries as a result of the introduction of inclusive education and the effective use of the latest innovative pedagogical technologies.

A positive attitude toward disability has been formed in society.

The school enrollment rate for children with special needs has increased to 85-98%. There has been a significant improvement in the qualifications of teachers. Socialization of students has significantly improved.

In particular, the first implementation of this system in Uzbekistan dates back to 2014. In cooperation with the Ministry of Preschool and School Education, the Center for Social Adaptation of Children, and the European Union, the "Inclusive Education" project was implemented in 15 schools across 5 regions of the republic, involving more than 800 children in inclusive classes.

In the early years, inclusive education was organized in the following regions:

1. Shaykhantakhur district of Tashkent city (324-34-85 schools);
2. Namangan city of Namangan region (schools 11-5-28);
3. Samarkand city of Samarkand region (schools 17-13-35-45);
4. Khorezm region, Urgench city (schools 10-8-22);
5. Surkhandarya region, Termez city (schools No. 3-4-10).

In recent years, the coverage of inclusive education in Uzbekistan has been increasing. While 12.4% of children with disabilities were enrolled in inclusive education in the 2020-2021 academic year, this figure is planned to reach 25% in 2024-2025; in the 2023-2024 academic year, this figure increased significantly, and inclusion was introduced in more than 1,400 schools.

A number of laws, resolutions, and decrees aimed at supporting the legal, universal, and social rights of these schools and inclusive education participants, and extending and protecting the hand of gratuitous assistance to them; the establishment of social centers to address any social and legal problems (National Agency for Social Protection under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan; Human social service centers) is a practical manifestation of Uzbekistan's approach to the model of developed countries in the world.

In inclusive education, it is required that the teacher does not organize the lesson at a uniform pace or passively; on the contrary, they involve students in the lesson through modern technologies, active, and engaging methods. To this end, the use of interactive methods and modern technologies—information and communication technologies (ICT), video lessons, audio materials, bright drawings, and graphic materials—is of great importance in improving the quality and effectiveness of education. The latest pedagogical technologies are being introduced into the education system of Uzbekistan in the fields of physics, biology, medicine, and inclusive education (virtual laboratories, 3D modeling, AR\VR classrooms).

Methodologically, VR stimulants allow students to conduct experiments in a safe environment, virtually simulate real-world conditions, and reinforce practical skills. Screen-reading programs (NVDA, JAWS), voice keyboards, smart classrooms, tactile materials, touch communication devices, and point-based mobile applications are being actively used in a number of specialized schools, parent centers, and inclusive classes in Uzbekistan. This, in turn, will significantly increase the effectiveness of education for students with disabilities and strengthen an inclusive environment.

Furthermore, in leading higher educational institutions such as the Nizami National Pedagogical University of Uzbekistan, Chirchik State Pedagogical University, and Jizzakh State Pedagogical University, the field of special pedagogy and its branches are gradually expanding and being introduced into the educational process based on modern approaches. Including in

our Andijan State Pedagogical Institute, starting from the 2022-2023 academic year, the direction of speech therapy was introduced as one of the important areas of special pedagogy, and a large number of students in this specialty were integrated into the educational process of the institute. This is also an example of the special attention paid by our state not only to children with special needs but also to personnel who provide them with quality education and upbringing.

In conclusion, inclusive education serves to create an adapted educational environment that rejects discrimination, segregation, and barriers for students with various developmental disabilities, aiming to create equal conditions and opportunities for all children. The effective implementation of this system requires close cooperation between special educators, general education teachers, psychologists, and parents.

In the process of inclusive education practice, the full involvement of special educators in the educational process, their encouragement, the formation of positive motivation, and the recognition of achievements in various forms (diplomas, certificates, etc.) serve to strengthen children's self-confidence, self-esteem, and social activity skills.

Furthermore, inclusive education requires psychological support not only for students but also for their parents. Providing parents with insights into the developmental possibilities, talents, and potential of their children, and turning them into active participants in the pedagogical process, is one of the important tasks of specialists working in this field.

Overall, the proper organization of inclusive education creates a foundation for strengthening the principles of tolerance, social justice, and cooperation in society, and for creating favorable conditions for the development of every child as an individual.

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